

**FEATURES OF TEACHING LATIN TO STUDENTS MEDICAL
UNIVERSITIES STUDYING IN ENGLISH**

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Abstract: The article deals with the problem of teaching Latin in English at a medical university. The purpose of this discipline is to prepare a terminologically competent doctor. It describes the specifics of teaching Latin in English, the difficulties that arise in the process of teaching it to foreign students, and how they are overcome. Special attention is paid to ways to optimize the learning process and develop motivation.

Key words: Latin language, teaching in English, medical terminology, terminoelements, aphorisms, motivation, general cultural development.

Following global educational trends, many leading Russian universities offer training in English. In our university, English-language programs for the first time began to be introduced in 2014 on the basis of medical institute. Students from different countries take a course in the specialty "Medicine".

This article will focus on teaching the discipline "Latin" in English in university. Latin is studied during first year of study. The textbook by D.K. Kondratiev and others is used as the main textbook, specially designed to study this discipline in English.

Latin is a completely new, previously unstudied discipline for first-year students, therefore causing certain difficulties in assimilation. In a medical school, Latin is taught by with the aim of instilling in students the basics of studying and using medical terminology, not only in university, but also in subsequent professional activities, in other words, to prepare terminologically competent doctor.

As a propaedeutic discipline, Latin is the most direct connected in a way with all disciplines studied in medical faculties, especially with anatomy, biology, biochemistry, microbiology, pharmacology, clinical disciplines.

Teaching Latin in English causes certain difficulties, especially for those students for whom it is not native. When studying Latin, special attention is paid to memorization of terms. Many words in English denoting terms have Greek-Latin origin, so mastering them is not difficult for a person who is fluent in English skim language. The situation is different for students whose native

language is Arabic or Chinese. In these languages, similar words can be completely different.

Students have to spend more time for their learning. The situation is even more tense with foreign students with poor language preparation. malleable. It happens that they do not know many English words, and the teacher has to spend more time to explain a particular term. The lexical minimum required to master the discipline (in the amount of 900 units), designed for strong memorization at the level of long-term memory.

These are the words and term elements selected according to the principle of frequency of use, thematic importance and word formation vocative valency. To facilitate memorization, the teacher can use the as social connections, for example: the word gaster [stomach] can be remembered using the familiar word gastritis.

Learning words is an integral part of the Latin language classes. Students start special notebooks for writing new words. Keeping notebooks is regularly checked. Words are memorized in words boiled form, which helps with grammar exercises. Unlike Russian students dents, foreign students hardly fulfill the requirements of the teacher, sometimes they can afford do not learn the necessary material, forget the notebook, textbook. As a result, the Latin language begins to seem complex and uninteresting. After conducting a survey among students about the difficulties of learning Latin, it was revealed that for many of them the main problems are: a large amount of time spent cramming, and a language barrier due to poor knowledge of English.

In addition to medical terminology, the classes also pay attention to Latin aphorisms and popular expressions that help not only to recognize the centuries-old wisdom, but also better memorize miss Latin words. At each lesson, the student is asked to memorize one or two aphorisms that to a certain extent "revive" the study of a "dead" language. Some aphorisms of the Latin language questions of life and death (*Vivere militare est.* / To live is to fight), human health (*Hygiena amica valetudinis.* / Hygiene is a friend of health), doctor behavior (*Medice, cura aegrotum, sed non morbum.* / Doctor, treat the patient, not the disease), are medical commandments (*Salus aegroti suprema lex medicorum.* / The benefit of the patient is the highest law of doctors; *Primum noli nocere!* / First of all, do no harm!). Thus, the problem of general cultural development of the student is also solved.

Teaching Latin in English has its own characteristics associated with both

the language barrier among some students, and with the organization of the learning process and knowledge control. Many students do not make it a rule to regularly attend classes and do their homework. In this regard, the learning process slows down and not all students by the end of the course form the necessary our knowledge, skills and abilities. Teaching in English means more work, patience, attention and energy expenditure on the part of the teacher. He needs to pay more attention to discipline and conversations of an educational nature.

So, the study of Latin is an integral part of the training of future doctors. Teaches- whether this discipline is in Russian or English, the goal remains the same - to create the basis of terminological of the professional language system. Of course, the conceptual content of terms can be complete and strictly disclosed only in the study of special disciplines in the relevant departments. Successful learning Latin will only contribute to their easier assimilation and application.

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